

Research article**Amsa Basti for the Treatment of Avabahuka w.r.t. Frozen Shoulder – Pilot Study**

Dr. Sonali D. Wairagade¹, Dr Ranjeet Z. Patil², Dr Tanvi D. Wairagade³, Dr Poonam Madan⁴, Dr. P.H. Hatwalne⁵

- 1. MD, MRAV, PhD scholar, Professor & HOD Department of Kayachitsa, Datta Meghe Ayurvedic Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Wanadongari, Nagpur*
- 2. BAMS, MD, Professor Department of Dravyaguna Yashwant Ayurvedic College Post Graduate Training and Research Centre, Kodoli, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India.*
- 3. MBBS, HBT Medical College and Dr. R N Cooper Hospital, Mumbai, Maharashtra*
- 4. BAMS, MD, Professor & HOD Department of Rasashastra and Bhashajyakalpana, Datta Meghe Ayurvedic Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Wanadongari, Nagpur*
- 5. Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, YCCE, Wanadongri, Nagpur (MS),*

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Sonali D. Wairagade

PhD scholar, Professor & HOD Department of Kayachitsa, Datta Meghe Ayurvedic Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Wanadongari, Nagpur

Abstract:**Background:**

Avabahuka is an illness that affects the Amsa sandhi in most cases (shoulder joint). The Vata dosha is responsible for its production. Despite the fact that the term Avabahuka does not appear in the nanatmaja Vata vyadhi, Avabahuka was recognized as a Vataja vikara by Acharya Sushruta and others. The disease's initial stage, known as amsa shosha (shoulder wasting), is characterized by the drying out or loss of sleshaka kapha of amsa sandhi.

Novelty: *Amsa basti is an innovative procedure. Amsa basti was given by a Novel Instrument called Amsa Basti Yantra which was invented by me.*

Method:

For the present study, Laghu Vishagarbha tail Amsa basti by Amsa basti yantra along with Trayodashang Guggulu was given to 15 patients for 21 days.

Results:

After treatment 79.49% relief was found on Shoola (pain), 81.82% relief was found on Stabdhata (Stiffness), 75% relief on Bahupraspanditahara Akunchana (Flexion), 78.26% relief on Prasarana (Extension), 68.42% relief on Avannamana (Adduction), 57.14% relief on Unnamanah (Abduction), 80% relief on Triyakgamana (Circumduction), 60.87% relief on Sparsha-asahishnuta (Tenderness). Three (20%) patients got marked improvement, Six(40%) got moderate improvement and Six (40%) were improved after 21 days of therapy in 15 Patients.

Conclusion:

Laghu Vishagarbha tail Amsa basti by Amsa basti yantra along with Trayodashang Guggulu provided a moderately significant effect on Shoola (pain), Stabdhata (Stiffness), Prasarana (Extension), Triyakgamana (Circumduction), Bahupraspanditahara Akunchana (Flexion) symptoms and a mildly significant effect on Prasarana (Extension), Unnamanah (Abduction), Sparsha-asahishnuta (Tenderness).

Keywords:

Avabahuka , Amsa basti , Laghu Vishagarbha tail, Trayodashang Guggulu , Frozen Shoulder

1. Introduction:

Avabahuka combines the words *ava* and *bahuka*. In this case, the words "*ava*" and "*bahu*" both refer to the arm. *Avabahuka* therefore means shoulder dysfunction.

The primary contributor to *avabahuka* is *vitiated Vata*^[1]. Although *Acharya Sushruta* and other *Acharyas* thought *Avabahuka* to be a *Vata vyadhi*, *Avabahuka* is not listed in *Nanatmaj Vatavyadhi*. *Amsa Sandhi* is afflicted with the illness known as *Avabahuk*.

Two stages of *Avabahuka* are described by *Madhavnidan*^[2]

- 1) *Amsashosha*[due to *vitiated Vata*]
- 2) *Avabahuka*[due to *vitiated Vata* and dryness of *sheshak kapha*]

Cardinal features of *Avabahuka* are-

Bahupraspandidahara^[3]- [difficulty or loss of movement of the upper limb], *Shoola*^[4]-[pain] *Amsabandhana Shosha*^[5]-[stiffness of shoulder joint].

In some *Ayurvedic* texts '*Apabahuka*' word is also used instead of '*Avabahuka*'. We will use the term "*Avabahuka*" throughout this study

Avabahuka is similar to Modern science's "Frozen Shoulder." Adhesive capsulitis, or stiff shoulder, is another name for the condition when stiffness of the shoulder joint coexists with joint discomfort.

Frozen shoulder is classified into two types; Primary and Secondary.

Primary Frozen Shoulder is idiopathic and Secondary Frozen Shoulder occurs due to systemic diseases like diabetes mellitus, hypothyroidism and injury or surgery.

The main symptoms of Frozen Shoulder are described in three stages ^[6]-1] Freezing 2] Frozen 3] Thawing stage.

2% of the general population is affected by frozen shoulder ^[7] with incidence of 2.4 per 1000 person/years. Before the age of 40 it is rare in human beings, more common in between age of 40 to 60 years of age. It is not common in patients above 60 years of age but frozen shoulder due to trauma or injury. Women are affected more than men. Reappearance of same symptoms in the same shoulder is not common but 20% of patients may develop same symptoms in other shoulder. In 14% of patients may feel symptoms of frozen shoulder in both joints and 80% of patients will experience reappearance of symptoms in five to six years. The condition that frequently goes hand in hand with frozen shoulder is diabetes mellitus ^[8].

Therefore, adequate therapy is required for the issue since *Avabahuka* significantly restricts daily living activities, which has a severe impact on quality of life and can result in long-term or even permanent disability in certain individuals.

The purpose of treatment is to reduce pain, improve range of motion, reduce disability, improve quality of life, and hasten rehabilitation and return to work.

The fundamental tenet of *Avabahuka* therapy in *Ayurveda* is *Vata Shaman chikitsa*. *Vatavyadhi*^[9] is typically treated using *Snehana*, *Swedana*, *Mrudusamshodhan*, *basti*, *Nasya*, and other methods. Due to its effectiveness, *Snehana- Swedana*^[10,11] for the treatment of *Avabahuka*, which is typically administered in *Vatavyadhi chikitsa*, has grown in popularity. Our study aims to see efficacy of *Laghu Vishagarbha tail* ^[12] *Amsa basti*^[13,14,15,16] and *Trayodashang Guggulu*^[17] for *Avabahuka*

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Settings:

Patients of both sex diagnosed with *Avabahuka* from the OPD and IPD of Datta Meghe Ayurved Medical College Hospital and Research Centre (DMAMCH&RC), Wanadongri, Nagpur (MS), were registered for the study.

2.2. Sample Size:

The present study explored the possible effectiveness of *Laghu Vishagarbha tail Amsa basti* by *Amsa basti yantra* along with *Trayodashang Guggulu* for the patients of *Avabahuka* (Frozen Shoulder). A total of 19 patients were registered for therapy, with four patients dropping out during the study's earlier phases. Fifteen individuals were treated for three weeks.

2.3. Design:

The present Pilot study is an experimental clinical trial of *Laghu Vishagarbha tail Amsa basti* along with *Trayodashang Guggulu* for the patients of *Avabahuka* (Frozen Shoulder) treated at DMAMCH&RC, Wanadongri, Nagpur (MS). All efficacy endpoints were evaluated after 3 weeks of treatment.

2.3. Patient selection:

a. Inclusion criteria:

1. Male Patients and Female Patients in the age group of 40 – 60 years
2. Patients with Freezing and Frozen stages of Frozen Shoulder
3. Patients having cardinal signs of *Amsa sandhi shoola* (shoulder pain), *Amsasandhi stabdhata* (shoulder stiffness), with or without *Amsasosha* (muscle

wasting), *Sparsha asahishnuta* (Local tenderness) , *Bahupraspandhitahara* (constrained movements of shoulder region)

4. Patients who were willing to take treatment after giving detailed description about therapy are included for the study.

b. Exclusion criteria:

1. Diagnosed cases of - Patients with Thawing stage of Frozen Shoulder
2. Dislocation of Shoulder joint
3. Radiating pain in Neck
4. Diabetes, Generalized arthritis
5. Fractures and dislocations of humerus
6. Cervical Spondylitis
7. Cardiopulmonary disease
8. Parkinson's disease
9. Rotator cuff tear, tendinitis
10. Pregnant and Lactating women
11. Autoimmune disorders like SLE and Rheumatoid Arthritis
12. Patients who refuse to participate in study will be excluded

2.4. Investigations:

1. CBC
2. RBS (Random blood sugar)
3. Urine – Routine and microscopic
4. X-Ray Shoulder joint — Antero-posterior and lateral view

2.5. Treatment plan:

After analysis, patients were treated with *Laghuvishagarbha tail Amsa Basti* for 21 days and *Trayodashang Guggulu* with plain water, 500 mg thrice a day for 21 days.

a. Method of *Amsa Basti*-

Amsa basti was mainly comprises of 3 steps.

Step 1: Pre-preparation of *Amsa basti* Treatment

Step 2: Main *Amsa basti* Treatment

Step 3: Post Treatment care

Step 1: Pre-preparation of *Amsa basti* Treatment

1. Treatment room was well-lit, ventilated and clean. The room temperature was maintained between 25-29°C during procedure. A changing area for patient with clean towel was arranged in the room.

2. Medicated Oil for treatment- Quantity of oil for each Treatment was 200-300ml
3. Heating system with temperature monitoring
4. The oil was poured along the wall of the *Amsa basti Yantra* rather than pouring it directly on the skin.
5. On an average a temperature of 40-45°C was well tolerated by the patients.
6. During the period of 25 to 30 minutes the temperature of oil was maintained automatically.
7. The treatment Chair
8. The oil collection, heating and filtration system
9. Dough - It was used to seal the instrument. It was made from Black Gram powder.
10. Patient's Position: *Amsa basti* was performed in the sitting position with relaxed body.

Step 2: Main *Amsa basti* Treatment Procedure:

Table 1:

Treatment Regime	Time
Each day treatment sitting	45 to 60 minutes
<i>Amsa basti</i> Therapy	20-30 minutes
Massage of Shoulder Joint	10 – 15 minutes
Rest after Therapy	10 minutes

Step 3: Post Treatment Care:

1. Patient was required to remain on the treatment chair for 10 to 15 minutes after completion of the procedure.
2. Treatment area was wiped off with a clean towel.
3. The patient's response to therapy was monitored at each follow-up visit
4. Care advice was given to patient after each session to avoid complication and to maximize the benefit of the therapy. Patient was advised to have light meals and rest for the remaining day.
5. Lukewarm bath was advised after 1-2 hour of completion of therapy.

2.6. Evaluation Criteria:

The evaluation was done according to Subjective and Objective parameters.

a. Subjective Parameters:

Amsasandhi shoola – pain in Shoulder Joint (Assessed by Visual Analogue Scale ^[18]).

Amsasandhi stabdhatta – stiffness

b. Objective Parameters:

Bahupraspandhitahara—constrained movements of shoulder region and Range of Movement for shoulder [flexion, extension, abduction, adduction, and circumduction] was calculated using a goniometer^[19].

Sparsha asahishnuta-Local tenderness

c. Subjective criteria for evaluation:**Table 2:**

Sr. No	Parameters	Symptoms	Scoring
1	<i>Shool</i> (Pain)	Absence of Pain	0
		Mild Pain [up to 3 marks]	1
		Moderate Pain [up to 4 – 6 marks]	2
		Severe Pain [up to 7 - 10 marks]	3
2	<i>Stabdhata</i> (Stiffness)	No Stiffness	0
		Mild- difficulty in movement of joints	1
		Moderate, has difficulty in moving hand, can lift affected hand only with support	2
		Severe, unable to lift	3

d. Objective criteria for evaluation:**Table 3:**

Sr. No.	Parameters	Symptoms	Scoring
1	<i>Bahupraspanditahara</i> <i>Akunchana</i> (Flexion)	161 ⁰ -180 ⁰	0
		81 ⁰ -160 ⁰	1
		10 ⁰ - 80 ⁰	2
		Cannot flex	3
2	<i>Prasarana</i> (Extension)	41 ⁰ - 60 ⁰	0
		21 ⁰ - 40 ⁰	1
		0 ⁰ - 20 ⁰	2
		Cannot extend	3

3	<i>Unnamanah</i> (Abduction)	161 ⁰ -180 ⁰	0
		81 ⁰ -160 ⁰	1
		10 ⁰ - 80 ⁰	2
		Cannot abduct	3
4	<i>Avannamana</i> (Adduction)	21 ⁰ - 30 ⁰	0
		11 ⁰ - 20 ⁰	1
		0 ⁰ - 10 ⁰	2
		Cannot adduct	3
5	<i>Triyakgamana</i> (Circumduction)	Normal	0
		Pain on Circumduction	1
		Circumduction with moderate pain	2
		Circumduction not possible due to stiffness	3
6	<i>Sparsha-asahishnuta</i> (Tenderness)	Absence of pain on pressure	0
		Pain on pressure	1
		Unpleasant affected part	2
		Does not allow to touch the affected part	3

e. Subjective and Objective parameters of *Avabahuka* were recorded before [BT] and after treatment [AT].

Data concerning above said parameters was collected:

1. Before treatment, day '0'
2. On 7th day
3. On 14th day
4. On 21stday

2.6. Statistical analysis:

To analyze statistically, observations were taken before and after treatment. Because the observations are on an ordinal scale (gradations), we utilized the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test to assess significance. The mean, percentage, SD, SE, and P-value were calculated from the observations recorded.

Criteria of assessment for overall therapy:**Table 4:**

Absolute relief	100% relief in all complaints
Marked relief	Up to 75% relief in all complaints
Moderate relief	Up to 50% relief in all complaints
Mild Improvement	25 to 50 %relief in the complaints.
Unchanged	< 25% relief in their complaints

3. Demographic Observations:**Table 5:**

Age group	
41-50 years	74%
51-60 years	26%
Sex	
Male	60%
Female	40%
Religion	
Hindu	51%
Muslim	28%
Christian	21%
Socioeconomic Status	
Low	40 %
Middle	46.66 %
High	13.33 %

4. Results

Laghu Vishagarbha tail Amsa basti by Amsa basti yantra along with Trayodashang Guggulu was given in 15 patients of *Avabahuka* (Frozen Shoulder) for 21 days. After treatment of 21 days 79.49% relief was found on *Shoola* (pain), 81.82% relief was found on *Stabdhatu* (Stiffness), 75% relief on *Bahupraspanditahara Akunchana* (Flexion), 78.26% relief on *Prasarana* (Extension), 68.42% relief on *Avannamana* (Adduction), 57.14% relief on

Unnamanah (Abduction), 80% relief on *Tiriyakgamana* (Circumduction), 60.87% relief on *Sparsha-asahishnuta* (Tenderness).

Synergistic outcome of therapy found on overall symptoms in 15 patients with *Avabahuka* - Three (20%) patients got marked improvement, Six (40%) got moderate improvement and Six (40%) patients got mild improvement after 21 days of therapy in 15 Patients.

Table 6:

Sr. No.	Main Symptoms		Mean	Median	SD	SE	Wilcoxon W	P-Value	% Effect	Result
1	Shoola (pain)	BT	2.60	3.00	0.83	0.21	-	0.00041	79.49	Sig
		AT	0.53	0.00	0.64	0.17	3.531 ^b			
2	<i>Stabdhatta</i> (Stiffness)	BT	2.20	2.00	0.77	0.20	-	0.00054	81.82	Sig
		AT	0.40	0.00	0.51	0.13	3.460 ^b			
3	<i>Bahupradpandita</i> <i>hara Akunchana</i> (Flexion)	BT	1.87	2.00	0.52	0.13	-	0.00041	75.00	Sig
		AT	0.47	0.00	0.52	0.13	3.535 ^b			
4	<i>Prasarana</i> (Extension)	BT	1.53	2.00	0.52	0.13	-	0.00102	78.26	Sig
		AT	0.33	0.00	0.49	0.13	3.286 ^b			
5	<i>Unnamanah</i> (Abduction)	BT	1.27	1.00	0.46	0.12	-	0.00177	68.42	Sig
		AT	0.40	0.00	0.51	0.13	3.127 ^b			
6	<i>Avannamana</i> (Adduction)	BT	0.93	1.00	0.59	0.15	-	0.00468	57.14	Sig
		AT	0.40	0.00	0.51	0.13	2.828 ^b			
7	<i>Tiriyakgamana</i> (Circumduction)	BT	2.33	2.00	0.49	0.13	-	0.00035	80.00	Sig
		AT	0.47	0.00	0.52	0.13	3.573 ^b			
8	<i>Sparsha-</i> <i>asahishnuta</i> (Tenderness)	BT	1.53	2.00	0.64	0.17	-	0.00496	60.87	Sig
		AT	0.60	1.00	0.51	0.13	2.810 ^b			

We utilised the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test to assess significance because the observations were on an ordinal scale (gradations). The table above shows that the P-value is less than 0.05. As a result, we may conclude that a substantial effect was observed in pain, stiffness, flexion, extension, adduction, abduction, circumduction, and tenderness.

Graph A-

Division according to relief in signs and symptoms:

5. Discussion:

In this competitive world pain is an annoying experience for anyone. If any part of body is having pain or stiffness then the person gets irritated, intolerant, and sometimes depressed. As pain makes individual's life difficult, *Avabahuka* is one of such condition due to which day to day life gets hampered.

Diagnosed *Avabahuka* cases were selected for the trial, and therapy was provided on an OPD and IPD basis. Subjective and objective measures were measured both before and after the treatment. Three follow-ups were conducted to assess *Avabahuka* symptoms. *Laghuvishagarbha tail Amsa Basti* and *Trayodashang guggulu* was given to 15 patients. In addition to the *Deepana Pachana* characteristics of *Trayodashang Guggulu*, medications such as *Guggulu* and *Abha resins* have *Rasayana* and *Balya* properties that restore damaged tissue, and *Rasna*, *Yavani*, works as *Vedana Sthapana* and *Vata Shamaka*. *Shunti*, *Daruharidra* plays

Shothahara.

The majority of the medications in Laghu Vishagabha Tail are Ushnaveerya and Vatashamaka. As a result, the combination has a pronounced Vatashamaka effect. The herbs used in this Tail have deep penetrating effects that reach the dermal levels, calming the nerves and cells beneath the skin and relieving pain.

The application of heat in the form of *Snehayukta Svedana* by *Laghuvishagarbha tail Amsa Basti* increases local circulation and metabolic activity while also opening the skin's pores to allow for the passage of medicaments and nutrients to essential areas as well as the elimination of vitiated Dosha and Mala through the skin and sweat. Heat applied to the skin increases metabolic activity, circulation, and stimulates nerve endings in the skin and tissues. It also has several indirect effects on the body's mechanisms. The use of medications, heat, and massage surely aids in the elimination of noxious elements through the skin. ^[20]

The study showed the results of different parameters as follows -

Shoola (Pain):

Prior to treatment, 2 patients experienced severe pain, 6 had moderate pain, and 7 had mild pain. After seven days of treatment, one patient had severe pain, five had moderate discomfort, eight had mild pain, and one had complete pain relief. After 14 days of treatment, there was only one patient with moderate pain, nine patients with light pain, and five patients who experienced complete pain relief. After 21 days of treatment, only one patient had moderate pain, six had light discomfort, and eight had complete pain relief.

Stabhdata (Stiffness):

The severity of Stabhdata (stiffness) before therapy and subsequent follow-up is as follows: Prior to treatment, there were six patients with severe Stabhdata (stiffness), six with moderate Stabhdata (stiffness), and three with light Stabhdata. After seven days of treatment, three patients had severe Stabhdata (stiffness), four had moderate Stabhdata (stiffness), seven had light Stabhdata (stiffness), and one had total relief from Stabhdata. At the end of 14 days, only 3 patients had moderate pain, while 6 patients had mild Stabhdata (stiffness) and 6 patients had complete relief of Stabhdata (stiffness). At the end of 21 days of treatment, 6 patients had mild Stabhdata (stiffness), and 9 patients had complete relief of Stabhdata (stiffness).

Prasarana (Extension)

The severity of Prasarana (extension) before therapy and subsequent follow-up is as follows: Prior to therapy, there were eight patients with moderate Prasarana (Extension) and seven with mild Prasarana (Extension). After 21 days of treatment, 10 patients had a normal Prasarana (Extension) angle of 410 - 600, whereas 5 had a Prasarana (Extension) angle of 210 - 400. Before treatment, the mean of Prasarana (Extension) was 1.53. Following 21 days of treatment, Prasarana (Extension) was 0.33.

Tiriyakgamana (Circumduction):

The severity of Tiriyakgamana (circumduction) before to therapy and subsequent follow-up is as follows:

Before treatment, 5 patients had severe Tiriyakgamana (Circumduction), and 10 had Tiriyakgamana with moderate discomfort. After 21 days of treatment, 8 patients had normal Tiriyakgamana (Circumduction), whereas 7 had slight pain on Tiriyakgamana. Prior to therapy, the mean Tiriyakgamana (Circumduction) was 2.33. After 21 days of treatment, Tiriyakgamana (Circumduction) was 0.47.

For all parameters when these data were subjected to contingency table analysis, the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test value was found to be significant (P value < 0.05).

Overall assessment of the result:

Synergistic outcome of therapy found on overall symptoms in 15 patients with *Avabahuka* - Three (20%) patients got marked improvement, Six (40%) got moderate improvement and Six (40%) patients got mild improvement after 21 days of therapy in 15 Patients.

It was observed that *Shoola*, *Bahupradpandita hara*, *Stambha*, physician assess and patient's assess showed significant progress. P test was used on these BT and AT scores since they comply with international standards. It demonstrated that the treatment's administration significantly decreased the severity of the illness (P 0.05).

6. Conclusion –

Conclusion was drawn from Observations of before treatment and After Treatment of the current study. Exhausting substantial work and harm are the prone factors in the demonstration of the ailment *Avabahuka*. Utmost prevalence of *Avabahuka* (Frozen Shoulder) was seen in the age group of 40-50 years. *Laghu Vishagarbha tail Amsa basti by Amsa basti yantra* along with *Trayodashang Guggulu* has provided a moderately significant effect on *Shoola* (pain),

Stabdhata (Stiffness), *Prasarana* (Extension), *Triyakgamana* (Circumduction), *Bahupraspanditahara Akunchana* (Flexion) symptoms and a mildly significant effect on *Prasarana* (Extension), *Unnamanah* (Abduction), *Sparsha-asahishnuta* (Tenderness). *Vatahara* line of treatment told by *Vagbhata*, *Sushruta* and *Charaka* for *Avabahuka* proves to be effective in the management of *Avabahuka*.

Due to small size of the sample we cannot illustrate generalized conclusion. *Amsa Basti* treatment can be experimented on a big sample to observe its proper efficacy

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Conflict of interest -

None

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